

Deep Neural Operator Surrogate Models for Light Water Reactor Design Optimization

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ABSTRACT

Data-driven approaches are increasingly applied in nuclear engineering to enhance reactor design and operational efficiency. While traditional core optimization methods based on high-fidelity simulations are widely used, they become computationally expensive when exploring a large design space of possible core loading patterns. To accelerate the optimization process, this work aims to assess the feasibility of an operator-learning-based surrogate model using the DeepONet architecture for fresh-core reactor optimization. The model is trained on datasets generated from a four-loop PWR calculations using the POLARIS/PARCS codes. It learns mappings between fuel assemblies characterized by two-group data from lattice calculations and key reactor physics responses, including spatial power distributions, cycle length, critical boron concentration, and pin peaking safety metrics. The surrogate achieves $R^2 > 0.99$ and mean absolute percent error $< 1.5\%$ for global parameters such as cycle length and peak critical boron concentration, while predicting local peaking factors (F_q and $F_{\Delta H}$) with $R^2 > 0.92$, showing a consistent underprediction trend within a 10% error range. The model is also adaptable to varying meshing schemes for non-uniform fuel assemblies. It achieves a 20–30 times speedup while maintaining satisfactory predictive accuracy. The proposed framework enables rapid and scalable reactor core optimization, extending the applicability of surrogate modeling beyond the limits of physics-based simulation approaches. Furthermore, the DeepONet architecture supports efficient transfer learning, enabling adaptation to new core designs or operating conditions with minimal retraining.

Keywords: Core Optimization, Operator Learning, Surrogate Model, Reduced Order Modeling

1. INTRODUCTION

The U.S. administration has recently signed executive orders to enhance energy security by promoting advanced reactor deployment and expanding nuclear energy capability. This initiative addresses the global challenge of reducing carbon emissions by 2050 while meeting doubled energy demand, requiring a transition from fossil fuels to low-carbon sources. Even though nuclear power remains the only proven, large-scale, carbon-free baseload source, it faces economic challenges from natural gas and renewables [1]. Enhancing its competitiveness mainly depends on improving fuel utilization and extending operating cycles through optimizing reactor core design. Core optimization involves arranging and managing numerous fuel assemblies (FAs) with varying enrichments and burnable poisons. The number of possible loading patterns (LPs) grows exponentially with the number of FA designs and distinct core locations defined by the selected symmetry, rendering the evaluation of a large portion of the design space infeasible. While modern simulators can assess a single LP in seconds, traditional optimization techniques like genetic algorithms (GA) [2] or simulated annealing (SA) [2] still require tens of thousands of evaluations, resulting in days of computation per case and covering only a fraction of the design space. This computational burden becomes prohibitive when considering the additional

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requirements for new FA designs, various burnup levels, and multi-cycle optimization across design criteria. To address this limitation, surrogate models have been introduced to quickly evaluate potential LPs while ensuring safety requirements in the optimization process. Yamamoto *et al.* [3] proposed using an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) with 2-dimensional (2D) k_∞ values in FA lattice calculations to predict core characteristics such as the radial peaking factor, cycle length, and maximum burnup for efficient screening in reactor optimization, demonstrating good performance with accelerated computation times. Similarly, [4] employed a convolutional neural network (CNN) within the C3-PLO framework for fresh core optimization, using principal component analysis (PCA) to extract the k_∞ curves for all FAs in the LPs as a three-dimensional (3D) array and achieving prediction errors below 3.0%. Butt *et al.* [5] extended neural network-based surrogates to equilibrium cycle optimization using the KNet structure. Particularly, the core reloading pattern was represented by an $8 \times 8 \times 5$ matrix encoding five assembly-level features—burnup, number of burn cycles, enrichment, zone symmetry, and burnable poison count—for 52 fuel assemblies in an 8×8 grid including void regions. The surrogate was coupled with a multi-objective GA to search for the optimal equilibrium cycle shuffling scheme. However, these previous approaches represent FAs using only 2D characteristics, such as k_∞ or design features, limiting their ability to capture complex FA designs with varying axial compositions and pin-level configurations. This study aims to develop a deep neural operator (DeepONet) [6]-based surrogate model for nuclear reactor core design optimization. The model's multi-branch DeepONet architecture learns the mapping between two-group cross-section data from lattice physics calculations and key reactor physics responses across complete operating cycles, including the 3D relative power distribution, cycle length, critical boron concentration (CBC), and pin peaking safety metrics. These responses are predicted at discrete depletion steps for different loading patterns. Training data is generated for Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) configurations using POLARIS/PARCS [7] for fresh core conditions with various FAs designs.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. DeepONet Architecture

DeepONet builds upon the universal approximation theorem for operators, which extends the classical function approximation theorem to operator learning. Chen and Chen [8] proved that a neural network with a single hidden layer can approximate any nonlinear continuous operator mapping between function spaces. Two primary architectural variants exist: stacked and unstacked configurations. The unstacked variant, illustrated in Fig. 1a, is more widely used as it outputs the entire feature vector from a single dense layer output of the branch network, whereas the stacked version employs separate neural networks for each element and concatenates their outputs to form the feature vector. In the unstacked architecture, the branch network encodes discrete input function evaluations at fixed sensor points $\{u(x_i)\}_{i=1}^m$ into feature vector $\mathbf{b} = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n]$, while simultaneously, the trunk network maps evaluation coordinate y to basis functions $\mathbf{t}(y) = [t_1(y), t_2(y), \dots, t_n(y)]$. The final output is then computed as $G(u)(y) = \sum_{i=1}^n b_i(u) t_i(y)$. During training, model parameters are optimized to minimize the discrepancy between the true operator output $\mathcal{G}(u)(y)$ and the DeepONet prediction as shown in the Eq. 1.

$$\min_{\theta} \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \mathcal{G}(u_i)(y_i) - \left\langle \underbrace{\mathbf{b}(u_i(x_1), u_i(x_2), \dots, u_i(x_m))}_{\text{branch}}, \underbrace{\mathbf{t}(y_i)}_{\text{trunk}} \right\rangle \right|^2}, \quad (1)$$

This decomposition consequently enables resolution-independent evaluation at arbitrary coordinates, maintains flexibility across geometric configurations and boundary conditions, and allows for independent optimization of branch and trunk components. However, the standard single-branch architecture has an important limitation: it cannot effectively handle problems with multiple input function families,

Figure 1. DeepONet architecture: unstacked variant (a) and multi-branch extension for reactor core analysis (b): spatial power distribution (Model 1) and reactivity parameters (Model 2)

such as systems where initial and boundary conditions or multiple physical fields jointly determine system response. Although concatenating inputs within a single branch is possible, this approach proves insufficient for capturing complex interactions. To overcome this constraint, the multi-branch DeepONet extension [9] assigns separate branch networks to different input functions as

$$G(u^{(1)}, u^{(2)}, \dots, u^{(k)})(y) = \sum_{i=1}^p \left(\prod_{j=1}^k b_i^{(j)}(u^{(j)}) \right) \cdot t_i(y), \quad (2)$$

where each branch network $b^{(j)}$ independently processes the input function $u^{(j)}$. The outputs from these branches are then combined through element-wise multiplication before computing the dot product with the trunk outputs. This extension enables learning of complex multi-input operators in high-dimensional parametric problems while maintaining resolution independence and implementation simplicity, and has been successfully applied across various scientific research areas [10].

2.2. DeepONet Applied for Reactor Core Calculation

For reactor design optimization requiring evaluation of thousands of configurations, PWR core analysis typically adopts the two-step approach to solve the neutron transport equation. First, detailed 2D lattice transport calculations capture neutron interactions within individual FAs and generate assembly-homogenized few-group cross sections with form factors for pin-level power reconstruction. Cross-sections are multi-parametrized on fuel temperature, moderator density, control rod insertion, and burnup, enabling core simulators to interpolate data for different reactor states. Second, core simulation codes solve multigroup 3D nodal diffusion equations shown in Eq. 3:

$$D_g \nabla^2 \phi_g - \Sigma_{a,g} \phi_g - \sum_{g'=g+1}^G \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g} \phi_{g'} + \sum_{g'=1}^{g-1} \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g} \phi_{g'} + \sum_{g'=1}^G \nu_{g'} \Sigma_{f,g'} \phi_{g'} = 0, \quad (3)$$

where ϕ_g is neutron flux in energy group g , D_g is the diffusion coefficient, $\Sigma_{a,g}$ is absorption macroscopic cross section, $\Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g}$ represents scattering between groups, and $\nu_{g'} \Sigma_{f,g'} \phi_{g'}$ is fission production rate. Core depletion analysis involves coupling whole-core neutronics with macroscopic depletion calculations to resolve the evolving burnup distribution. A typical predictor-corrector scheme updates burnup using the weighted power from consecutive depletion steps. Particularly, it calculates burnup change

as $\Delta E^k = \Delta E \left(RPF_i^k W_i + RPF_{i+1}^k W_{i+1} \right)$, where ΔE^k is burnup change in node k , RPF_i^k is relative power fraction at step i , W_i and W_{i+1} are weighting coefficients at step i and step $i + 1$ respectively. The process starts with $W_i = 1.0$, $W_{i+1} = 0.0$ for initial prediction, then recalculates with $W_i = W_{i+1} = 0.5$ after obtaining RPF_{i+1}^k , iterating until it converges within a predefined tolerance.

$$RPF^k = \frac{P^k \times V}{\bar{P} \times v^k} \rightarrow \sum_k \frac{v^k}{V} \times RPF^k = \frac{\sum_k P^k}{\bar{P}} = 1, \quad (4)$$

where P^k is the power in node k , V and v^k represent the total core region volume and the volume of node k , respectively, and \bar{P} is the nominal power value. To reduce the computational cost of core-depletion calculations, the DeepONet architecture is employed to build a surrogate model that treats the relationship between few-group parameters and core power distribution as an operator learning problem. The solution operator \mathcal{G} maps spatially dependent few-group cross sections for each fuel assembly to the corresponding 3D power distribution at each depletion step. The trunk network receives 3D spatial coordinates of computational nodes to capture spatial dependencies, while the input and output share identical spatial resolution, ensuring consistency across the core geometry. This aligned structure (branch inputs and outputs correspond to the same depletion step) simplifies training and preserves temporal consistency. Since core design analysis also depends on global integral parameters such as cycle length and CBC, a second neural operator is trained to predict these quantities as functions of depletion time. This model uses the same branch inputs but a temporal trunk network, enabling it to capture reactivity evolution throughout the fuel cycle.

2.3. Data generation

Within the scope of this study, the data generation was conducted for a generic four-loop PWR core based on the Westinghouse AP1000 design [11] with 193 FAs in a 17×17 lattice configuration containing 24 guide tubes and one central instrumentation tube. The core height was 426.72 cm with a 365.76 cm active fuel region including top and bottom blankets. The FAs comprise segments with enrichment levels of 4.50, 4.60, 4.95, 5.25, 5.65, and 5.85 wt%. Gd_2O_3 burnable absorber rods at 8.0 wt% concentration were used for all FAs, ranging from 16 to 32 absorber rods per assembly. Seven distinct FA types were considered, with specifications in Table I. All assemblies employ a 4.50 wt% enriched blanket region. Few-group cross-section data were generated through lattice calculations over a wide range of

Table I. FA specifications for AP1000 reactor core design

FA Label	Enrichment (wt%)	Number of Gd_2O_3 Rods
461	4.60	24
462	4.60	28
501	4.95	16
502	4.95	20
526	5.25	32
566	5.65	32
586	5.85	24

operating conditions, including fuel temperature variations, boron-free moderator states, and moderator density changes. POLARIS performed lattice physics calculations producing $t16$ output files with few-group nuclear data, which GenPMax [7] processed to create functionalized cross-section representations for interpolation across the parameter space. The processed library was formatted for PARCS 3D whole-core calculations. The core was discretized into a 9×9 radial mesh representing one-quarter core symmetry and 18 axial nodes (2 for axial reflectors, 6 non-uniform for blanket regions, 10 uniform

for fuel region). FA types from Table I were randomly assigned to generate 10,000 loading patterns, each depleted to 30.0 MWd/MTU across 34 burnup steps. Non-convergent cases were discarded, yielding over 300,000 depletion points for training. Each valid LP simulation required approximately 50 seconds for a complete core cycle depletion calculation. Random sampling mitigated the heuristic biases introduced during the optimization process, leading to a more balanced and unbiased dataset.

2.4. Data processing and Surrogate Model Architecture

The two DeepONet models proposed in the previous section are developed using spatial-dependent XS in nominal condition as input data. The first model outputs a $9 \times 9 \times 16$ (excluding two axial nodes that correspond to the reflector regions from the total of 18 axial nodes) matrix representing the 3D, assembly-wise RPF at a given depletion step. The second model focuses on global characteristics by predicting the CBC and cycle length at the corresponding depletion step. Before being fed into the model, the training data is normalized using a scaling range of min -50% to max $+50\%$, providing a wider coverage to account for extrapolation. Following dataset generation, the complete dataset is split into training and testing subsets using the 80-20 split ratio. The training data serves to train the DeepONet's branch and trunk network parameters through backpropagation and gradient descent algorithms, while the testing data provides an unbiased validation data set to evaluate the model's predictive performance on unseen data. The models were built with TensorFlow library and trained using RMSE as the loss function. The hyperparameters obtained from the grid search are summarized in Table II. Both models share the same tapered branch network architecture with 3 hidden layers, using an exponentially decaying learning rate starting at 5×10^{-4} . However, their trunk networks slightly differ: Model 1 uses a 3-input trunk for spatial coordinates with a batch size of 32, while Model 2 employs a 1-input trunk for temporal burnup with a batch size of 64. With the Adam optimizer, both models were trained on 80 CPUs and converged after roughly 200,000 iterations, requiring approximately 2,000 seconds. Convergence was identified when the loss, averaged over a 100-iteration moving window, stabilized.

Table II. Training parameters and network architecture for two DeepONet models

Parameters	Model 1	Model 2
Branch network	1,296 \rightarrow 800 \rightarrow 600 \rightarrow 400 \rightarrow 200	1,296 \rightarrow 800 \rightarrow 600 \rightarrow 400 \rightarrow 200
Trunk network	3 \rightarrow 500 \rightarrow 300 \rightarrow 200	1 \rightarrow 500 \rightarrow 300 \rightarrow 200
Learning rate	5×10^{-4}	5×10^{-4}
Batch size	32	64

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Predictive performance using burnup data extracted from PARCS

To isolate the model performance from error propagation in the coupled depletion process, the surrogate models were first evaluated independently at each depletion step using burnup distributions from PARCS for XS interpolation. The predicted 3D RPF, cycle length, and CBC were then compared against the corresponding PARCS reference data. The ground truth scattering plot for RPF is given in Fig. 2a. The red data points are densely clustered along the 0% error line, showing that the model consistently reproduces the ground truth with high accuracy. Most of the predictions fall within the $\pm 5\%$ error region, confirming that deviations are minimal. For both the CBC and cycle length, the predictions show good agreement with the ground truth, with differences remaining within 5 ppm for CBC and 20 days for cycle length, as illustrated in Fig. 2c and Fig. 2b, respectively. These deviations correspond to prediction errors of less than 5%, confirming the reliability of the surrogate model for

core global parameters. The results show a high $R^2 > 0.9995$, indicating a strong correlation between predicted and reference values. The Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE) values, all below 0.35%, highlight the model's ability to capture both local and global trends with minimal discrepancy. Similarly, the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) values of 0.12% for 3D RPF, 0.25% for CBC, and 0.27% for cycle length demonstrate that the model maintains high predictive accuracy across the desired parameters. Additionally, the resolution-independent nature of DeepONet permits evaluation

Figure 2. Comparison of surrogate predictions using PARCS burnup: (a) 3D RPF predicted vs. ground truth; (b) Cycle length error distribution; (c) CBC error distribution.

on arbitrary spatial discretizations. A testing of this capability was performed using randomly generated LPs with non-uniform axial meshes differing from the uniform discretization scheme used in the training process. Despite this mesh discrepancy, the model achieved 0.99430 in R^2 , 1.33% in NRMSE, and 1.07% in MAPE for 3D RPF predictions. The best and worst performing cases by RMSE are shown in Fig. 3a and 3b, respectively. This capability is essential for practical core design, where varying FA axial compositions mesh without model retraining.

Figure 3. 3D RPF predictions using PARCS burnup for non-uniform axial mesh. Reference solutions (center) compared against model predictions (left) and difference (right) for: (a) Best case (minimum RMSE); (b) Worst case (maximum RMSE).

3.2. Model Performance integrated with macro depletion calculation

After validating the surrogate model's performance for power distribution and global parameters, it was coupled with depletion calculations using the predictor–corrector approximation. The model predicts RPF at each time step, which updates the spatial burnup distribution via the predictor–corrector scheme with step size ΔE as described previously. Updated burnup distributions are then used for few-group cross-sections interpolation for subsequent branch network inputs, enabling iterative surrogate-

depletion coupling throughout the reactor cycle. Coupled depletion calculations show slightly degraded accuracy: 3D RPF predictions yield R^2 of 0.99885 where NRMSE and MAPE are 0.31%, 0.18%, respectively, with errors ranging within 10%. Global parameters achieve 0.99832 in R^2 for peak value of CBC and 0.99379 for cycle length, with NRMSE and MAPE both below 1.5%. When evaluating reactor safety, it is also necessary to account for pin-level safety parameters. Since the surrogate model predicts power only at the assembly level, it does not capture detailed intranodal flux shapes or the effects of neighboring assemblies. Therefore, to estimate critical safety metrics F_q (pin peaking factor) and $F_{\Delta H}$ (enthalpy rise hot channel factor), pin-level shape functions from lattice calculations were applied to assembly-level predictions. Figures 4a and 4b compare predicted and PARCS-calculated maximum $F_{\Delta H}$ and F_q values for each core configuration. While predictions show strong correlation with most values within $\pm 5\%$ error, an underestimation of 5–10% is observed for both pin peaking parameters. This underestimation mainly comes from two sources. First, the assembly-level reconstruction methodology neglects inter-assembly flux interactions, causing pin power distributions within each assembly to underpredict local maxima. Second, since pin peaking factors are derived from predicted 3D RPF rather than directly predicted, the model optimizes global RMSE across all assemblies, which inherently reduces accuracy in capturing extreme values. This RMSE-based optimization prioritizes average prediction quality over peak value accuracy, resulting in systematic underestimation of maximum pin powers that propagate to both F_q and $F_{\Delta H}$ predictions. Moreover, the surrogate provides substantial computational efficiency, reducing full-core depletion time from 50 seconds (PARCS) to 1.75 seconds—a 20–30 times speedup. This acceleration enables practical evaluation of thousands of core configurations previously constrained by computational cost. The consistent underestimation pattern does not impede optimization efficiency, as all candidates are evaluated with the same bias, and optimal solutions identified by the surrogate are subsequently verified using PARCS.

Figure 4. Comparison of surrogate models' prediction on pin safety parameters. (a) Comparison of peak $F_{\Delta H}$ in each cycle between PARCS reference and model prediction using assembly-level reconstruction; (b) Comparison of peak F_q in each cycle between PARCS reference and model prediction using assembly-level reconstruction.

4. CONCLUSION

This research developed and validated a DeepONet-based surrogate modeling framework for nuclear reactor core design optimization, addressing the computational bottleneck that limits traditional simulation approaches. The multi-branch DeepONet architecture learns operator mappings between fuel assembly characteristics and physics responses, including spatial power distributions, cycle length, and core safety metrics. The surrogate was trained on datasets generated for a conventional PWR core using POLARIS/PARCS for multiple LPs based on random sampling approach. The model achieves good performance for global parameters: CBC and cycle length predictions maintain $R^2 > 0.99$ and MAPE $< 1.5\%$. Local peaking factors (F_q and $F_{\Delta H}$) exhibit 5–10% errors with systematic underestimation, which arises from assembly-level homogenization neglecting inter-assembly effects and RMSE-based training that prioritizes global accuracy over local maximum. The surrogate completes full-core de-

pletion calculations in 1.75 seconds versus 50 seconds for PARCS, resulting a 20–30x speedup enabling practical evaluation of more core configurations. Future developments will quantify pin power reconstruction uncertainty and improve training methodologies that simultaneously optimize local peak prediction and global accuracy. The surrogate model will be integrated into the MIDAS optimization framework with a hybrid adaptive retraining strategy that strategically recalibrates predictions during optimization, enabling acceleration of existing optimization algorithms while maintaining solution fidelity.

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